

BOOSTING THE MOST IMPORTANT SKILLS OF ENGLISH BY USING DIFFERENT TYPES OF STRATEGIES AND GAMES.

Valiyeva Zarifa Ibrohim qizi

Student of Chirchik State Pedagogical University
valiyevazari45@gmail.com

Axmedova Muyassar Ataxanovna

Supervisor:

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Annotation. Nearly all of the foreign language learners can have some difficulties in the process of studying. Unfortunately, it can cause losing the motivation. In order to develop the skills of the language being learned people use only techniques. But not all of them know that the games also can improve the language learning skills. In this article various types of methods and games are described. Using these kinds of strategies help to boost learning skills.

Key words: Foreign languages, strategies, language learners, games and methods, English language, reading skills, vocabulary skills.

Annotatsiya. Chet tilini o'rganuvchilarning deyarli barchasi o'qish jarayonida ba'zi qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishi mumkin. Afsuski, bu motivatsiyani yo'qotishiga olib kelishiga ham sabab bo'ladi. O'rganilayotgan til ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun odamlar faqat metodlardan foydalanadilar. Ammo ularning hammasi ham o'yinlar til o'rganish ko'nikmalarini yaxshilashi mumkinligini bilmaydi. Ushbu maqolada turli xil usullar va o'yinlar tasvirlangan. Ushbu turdagi strategiyalardan foydalanish o'rganish ko'nikmalarini oshirishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Chet tillari, strategiyalar, til o'rganuvchilar, o'yin va metodlar, o'qish malakalari, so'z boyligi.

Аннотация. Практически у всех изучающих иностранный язык могут возникнуть определенные трудности в процессе изучения. К сожалению, это может привести к потере мотивации. Для развития навыков изучаемого языка люди используют только . Но не все из них знают, что игры также могут улучшить навыки изучения языка. В этой статье описаны различные виды методов и игр. Использование таких стратегий помогает улучшить навыки обучения.

Ключевые слова: Иностранные языки, методы, люди изучающие язык, игры и методы, навыки чтения, словарный запас.

The process of learning not only English but also any other foreign language depends on how and what kinds of methods and games are used. In addition to

this there is a significant difference in the knowledge of English learners in the very early stages of learning the language and those who have been learning the language for a long time. And therefore, it is advisable to use methods appropriate to the knowledge level of each learner. The use of various strategies and games in the process of language learning facilitates the development of important skills in English. The most important skills include reading, writing, listening, vocabulary and communication. According to E. I. Passov, communication is always rational and emotional, in the interaction between people through language, commonality is manifested, thoughts, and a way of life are formed. This is the most important condition for the formation of a person's consciousness and self-awareness [1]. Not only can methods help in the language learning process, but games can also improve the skills of language learners. There are games that can improve all the most important skills of language learners.

As mentioned in the introduction, materials and methods should be used according to the learner's level of knowledge to develop knowledge and skills. It is effective to use games that are more useful for students who are just learning English. Here is some of effective games for foreign language learners: Wordshake, ESL Crossword Puzzle, and etc. These types of games work like real dynamite to increase vocabulary, grammar and communication skills while playing this game, thinking and vocabulary expansion are provided. **Wordshake.** The player playing this game is given random letters of the alphabet, using these letters, they must make English words from these letters in just 3 minutes. For each correctly formed word, the player is given 1 point. This game is very suitable for both beginners and experienced learners. The main reason is that in this entertaining game, you can create and learn not only simple words, but also words that are difficult in terms of pronunciation. **ESL Crossword Puzzle.** All puzzles and questions in the game are specially designed for learners who are learning a foreign language and reaching the highest levels of language proficiency. Solving crosswords helps to develop reading skills, grammar and vocabulary. All crosswords are divided by difficulty level and grouped into specific categories. This gives learners a great opportunity to expand their vocabulary, learn the most common English words, or test their knowledge in another area. Everyone really wants to learn English or other languages through games. Because it is easy and convenient, and learning does not tire the learner at all, and there are many advantages. But they should not forget why they are playing games. They must make sure that learning English through games does

not turn into just playing video games. If their games have an English interface, that is good. Many games have good dubbing and a lot of dialogues, which makes the language learning process even easier. In general, it is very wonderful. This is enough for them to gradually improve their English. It is worth mentioning that learning foreign languages should not be limited to learning through games. One of the main reasons is that learners' knowledge level can become stagnant, therefore, it is necessary to focus on improving the language learner's basic reading, writing, listening, and speaking skills by using a variety of methods. The most effective methods for developing language skills include reading books and stories, listening to podcasts and audios, watching movies and short films as well. There are three aspects of language phenomena: language, speech, speech activity. The main types of speech activity were identified L.V. Sherbov, but one aspect of language he considered speech activity. He proposed to distinguish three aspects of language: speech, i.e. the process of speaking and understanding; language, ordered linguistic experience; linguistic material, unordered linguistic experience [2]. English learners tend to learn words by rote, and learning individual words leads to rapid word forgetting. There is no doubt that memorizing them without context is pointless. Instead, it is necessary to learn whole phrases. If they know the meaning of words and how they are used in a sentence, it is much easier to remember their meaning. Teachers should teach ESL classroom with materials reach high standards of knowledge. They should also work to create conditions that are necessary and important for learners so that students can effectively acquire knowledge and achieve the desired results. For English language teaching to be successful, the four skills (reading, listening, speaking, and writing) must be effectively integrated. These skills should be viewed in such a way that they help students meet the established standards and gradually develop their communicative competence [3]. If learners want to improve their English, they should avoid using the strategy used in many English textbooks, namely repeating the spoken word back to them. They should not repeat words or phrases mindlessly, but instead, they should answer the questions asked. For example, if language learners are listening to a podcast or watching a video, they should stop it every 30 seconds and write a short summary or self-description of the information being said. By using such methods, language learners can significantly improve their knowledge and skills.

Learning any language is both difficult and easy. Language serves many purposes. A lack of language is simply a lack of communication. The role of

language has been considered very important since ancient times. The four essential factors of language, or as they are popularly called, the four skills - reading, writing, listening and speaking - play an important role in learning any language. The four skills are the pinnacles of language, which are the factors that take learners to great heights. They are separate but inextricably linked to each other[3]. It is necessary to use effective methods and games that accelerate and facilitate the process of learning any language. Since each learner has his own characteristics, each foreign language learner should use strategies that are convenient and suitable for him. Any convenient games and methods can help develop the knowledge and skills of the language learner, if they use the methods correctly and play the games in moderation.

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